

Can use the Biotic Index as an indication of fish farm pond water quality?

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ABSTRACT:

The aim of this study is to determine fish farm pond's water quality by using aquatic insect. Monthly samplings have been conducted in five fish farms (Layo, Banco, Azaguié, Anyama I and Anyama II) in southern Côte d'Ivoire. In each pond, samples were collected in water column using a hand-net and in the sediment using a van Veen grab. Environmental variables were measured *in situ*. Water samples were taken and conducted to the laboratory where analyses of dissolved inorganic nutrients were carried out. A total of 79 taxa belonging to 35 families and 8 orders were recorded. Aquatic insect's fauna richness is clearly dominated by Heteroptera, Coleoptera and Diptera. Chironomidae was the most diverse family. Order Heteroptera was numerically the dominant taxa. The water quality is changing both spatially and temporally. Spatially, FBI values ranged from 1.61 to 3.41. This study revealed that water quality of the pond is excellent as supported by the values of biological index.

Keyword: *aquatic insects, fish farm ponds, Hilsenhoff Family Biotic Index, water quality, Côte d'Ivoire.*

INTRODUCTION

Fish is an inexpensive source of protein and an important cash crop in many regions of world and water is the physical support in which they carry out their life functions such as feeding, swimming, breeding, digestion and excretion [1]. Water, the most important component for raising fish, is often the most neglected factor. Fish are totally dependent on water; they derive oxygen from it, ingest it, excrete their wastes into it, absorb and lose salts into it, and are always in contact with it [2]. So, good water quality is very essential for survival and growth of fish. As we know fish is an important protein rich food resource and there has been sharp increase in demand of fish products due to increasing population pressure in this century. Thus to meet the demand of present food supply, water quality management in fish ponds is a necessary step that is required to be taken up [3]. Water quality is the first most important limiting factor in pond fish production. It is also the most difficult production factor to understand, predict and manage. Water is not just where the fish live. Its quality directly affects feed efficiency, growth rates, the fish's health and survival. Most fish kills, disease outbreaks, poor growth, poor feed conversion efficiency and similar management problems are directly related to poor water quality. Water quality includes all physical, chemical, and biological factors that influence the beneficial use of water. There are many water quality variables in pond aquaculture, but only a few of these normally play an important role [4]. Water quality is determined by various physico-chemical and biological factors, as they may directly or indirectly affect its quality and consequently its suitability for the distribution and production of fish and other aquatic animals [5]. There are several ways to assess water quality in lotic and lentic waterbodies, the most common methods focus on physical and chemical properties, such as the level of dissolved oxygen, mercury, and water clarity [6]. In lotic (running waters) systems, macroinvertebrates have been widely used as reliable water

quality indicators [7-8]. This is not true for lentic systems (ponds and lakes). In the past, indicators for lentic systems such as ponds still under development. Using macroinvertebrates for the determination of pond's water quality is recent. Scientific interest in this way has increased over the past decade. Indeed, scientific and practical basis for pond conservation in Europe are enhanced by the initiative of European Pond Conservation Network (EPCN) with publications, meetings and conferences providing scientific studies and instruments in progress to assess life quality and conservation. Water quality assessment as a expression for environment quality (biotic integrity or degradation) for wetlands, channels, lakes and ponds is attended by a various methods, applied on local or regional scale, mostly based on invertebrates, especially aquatic insects species abundance, at local or metacommunities level, diversity indices, multimetric indices [9-11]. The aim of this study is to ascertain some fish farm pond's water quality by using aquatic insect.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study sites

This study was undertaken in five fish farms in the southern region of Côte d'Ivoire characterized by four seasons (two dry and two rainy seasons). The dry seasons extend from December to March and from August to September while the rainy ones extend from April to July and from October to November. Sampling sites were assigned to habitat types according to environmental and ecological features: Aquaculture Experiment Station of Layo (05°19'N; 04°18'W), fish farms of Banco (05°23'N; 04°03'W), Azaguié (05°39'N; 04°05'W), Anyama I (05°33'N; 04°03'W) and Anyama II (05°34'N; 04°02'W) (Figure 1). Banco site is located in National Park of Banco which surrounding ecosystem comprised of primary forest. In Azaguié, Anyama I and Anyama II, surrounding ecosystems comprised of agricultural landscape and at Layo site, immediate environment was characterized by

habitation.

Figure 1. Location of the study area showing the different stations. The main water supplies were different in the sites: ponds in Anyama I and Azaguié were fed respectively by a man-made lake and a stream, ponds in Banco by Banco River, ponds in Anyama II by groundwater and ponds in Aquaculture Experimental Station of Layo by coastal aquifer. Ponds located in this last site were fed by brackish water (salinity ranging from 0 to 10 mg/L [12] while in the four others sites, ponds were supplied with fresh water. All ponds at all sites were permanent and were shallow (depth < 1 m). In each site, three ponds were randomly selected for this study. Pond area varied from 280 m² to 800 m². Bottom sediment are mostly composed by sand in Layo and Azaguié stations, by mud

in Banco, sand and clay in Anyama I while in Anyama II station, mud and sand were the dominant substrat. *Tilapia Oreochromis niloticus* Linnaeus, 1758 is the only fish species breded in the different fish farm ponds except Banco where pond were abandoned. In each site, ponds were originally man-made. The rice bran was the food provided to the fish. Feeding frequency was 3 sessions per day. Density of loading is from 3 to 5 fish/m² (Layo), 6 fish/m² (Azaguié and Anyama II) and 7 fish/m² (Anyama I).

Aquatic insect collection

In each pond, samples were collected monthly from December 2007 to November 2008. Each farm environmental variables and insects were respectively measured and sampled on the same day. One farm is sampled per day. Water column and sediment were sampling using a 350 µm mesh hand net and a Van veen grab (area = 0.09 m²) respectively. Each habitat was sampled in six replicates. The water column and sediment samples collected were respectively sieved through 300 µm and 1 mm aperture size sieve. The materials retained were preserved *in situ* in 10% formalin. In the laboratory, specimens were sorted and identified to the lowest possible taxonomic level (species, genus, family) by means of the keys in [13-16] and Gattoliat (personal communication). The aquatic insect assemblage composition was determined for each sampling station and sampling occasion using number of taxa, total number of individuals, and relative abundance of each taxon. The Family Biotic Index (FBI) [17] was used to assess the ecological integrity of the habitats. The formula for calculating the Family Biotic Index is: $FBI = \sum \frac{n_i \times a_i}{N}$

Where

n_i is the number of individuals of the i^{th} taxon; a_i is the tolerance value of that taxon and N is the sum of individual numbers in all the families making up the sample. In the FBI, an increasingly high score indicates lower water quality (Table 1). The higher the score is, the more the habitat is likely to be affected by stress. The index values (a_i) used in the equation are related to how well the family can tolerate organic pollutants, increased nutrient and sediment loads and dissolved oxygen (DO) limitations [18].

Table1. Evaluation of water quality using the family-level biotic index (Hilsenhoff, 1988).

Family Biotic Index	Water Quality	Degree of Organic Pollution
0.00-3.75	Excellent	Organic pollution unlikely
3.76-4.25	Very good	Possible slight organic pollution
4.26-5.00	Good	Some organic pollution probable
5.01-5.75	Fair	Fairly substantial pollution likely
5.76-6.50	Fairly poor	Substantial pollution likely
6.51-7.25	Poor	Very substantial pollution likely
7.26-10.00	Very poor	Severe organic pollution likely

Table 2. Physicochemical characteristics (mean ± (SD)) of water at various sampling stations.

Parameters	Stations				
	Layo	Banco	Azaguié	Anyama I	Anyama II
Secchi disk transparency (cm)	21.65±6.84 ^a	30.14±4.26 ^b	22.05±7.65 ^a	21.99±5.03 ^a	23.05±4.73 ^a
Temperature (°C)	28.36±1.11 ^b	27.20±0.60 ^a	28.97±1.10 ^b	28.80±1.07 ^b	28.80±0.88 ^b
Dissolved oxygen (mg.L ⁻¹)	5.55±1.32 ^b	4.18±1.15 ^a	5.71±0.66 ^{bc}	6.33±0.44 ^d	6.16±0.40 ^{cd}
pH	6.93±0.11 ^b	6.75±0.19 ^a	6.90±0.11 ^b	7.08±0.12 ^c	7.04±0.16 ^c
Conductivity	3037.83±2980.25 ^b	35.85±2.88 ^a	38.05±4.08 ^a	71.22±14.10 ^a	49.14±16.67 ^a

($\mu\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$)					
Nitrite ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	1.26 \pm 0.84 ^b	0.93 \pm 0.81 ^{ab}	1.02 \pm 0.55 ^{ab}	0.62 \pm 0.57 ^a	1.06 \pm 0.44 ^b
Ammonium ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	0.23 \pm 0.30 ^{ab}	0.31 \pm 0.36 ^b	0.17 \pm 0.26 ^{ab}	0.16 \pm 0.20 ^{ab}	0.12 \pm 0.16 ^a
Phosphate ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	2.47 \pm 1.44 ^b	2.08 \pm 0.86 ^b	2.05 \pm 1.21 ^b	1.09 \pm 0.69 ^a	2.10 \pm 0.79 ^b

a, b, c, d; letters showed the difference between the stations as regards the parameter indicated.

Table 3. List of families and abbreviation code

Orders	Families	Abbreviation
Coleoptera	Hydrophilidae	Hydr
	Dytiscidae	Dyti
	Spercheidae	Sper
	Gyrinidae	Gyri
	Elmidae	Elmi
	Curculionidae	Curc
	Chrysomelidae	Chry
Heteroptera	Leptopodidae	Lept
	Belostomatidae	Belo
	Gerridae	Gerr
	Corixidae	Cori
	Notonectidae	Noto
	Naucoridae	Nauc
	Pleidae	Plei
	Mesoveliidae	Meso
	Veliidae	Veli
	Nepidae	Nepi
Hydrometridae	Hydrom	
Diptera	Chironomidae	Chiro
	Ceratopogonidae	Cera
	Culicidae	Culi
	Chaoboridae	Chao
	Tabanidae	Taba
Odonata	Coenagrionidae	Coen
	Gomphidae	Gomp
	Libellulidae	Libe
Ephemeroptera	Caenidae	Caen
	Baetidae	Baet
	Polymitarcyidae	Polym

Trichoptera	Ecnomidae	Ecno
	Hydropsychidae	Hydro
	Polycentropodidae	Polyc
	Hydroptilidae	Hydrop
Lepidoptera	Pyralidae	Pyra
Megaloptera	Corydalidae	Cory

Environmental variables collection

On each sampling date, environmental variables such as transparency, temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen and conductivity were measured *in situ* between 08.00 and 10.00 a.m. Water temperature, pH and electric conductivity were measured using a multiparameter digital meter (WTW pH/Cond 340i). Dissolved oxygen concentration was measured with a WTW Oxi 92 oxygen meter and water transparency was determined using a 20-cm-diameter Secchi disk. Water samples were collected on every sampling day, filtered through GF/C Whatman filters, frozen upon arrival at laboratory. Analyses of dissolved inorganic nutrients (ammonium, NH_4^+ ; nitrite, NO_2^- and phosphate, PO_4^{3-}) from filtered samples were carried out according to [19].

Data analyses

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to assess the spatial effect on environmental variables. Before performing the comparison test, the normality of data was checked by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Data were $\log_{10}(X+1)$ transformed prior to analysis. A comparison of the data collected at different stations was made using one-way ANOVA and Tukey's *post hoc* test. Analyses were conducted using Statistica 7.1 software. The distribution of aquatic insects in all sampling stations were determined by Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) using CANOCO 5.0 software. Abbreviation of all taxa family are listed in Table 3.

Table 4. Number of species, number of families, number of orders and abundance of aquatic insects collected in the different stations.

	Banco	Layo	Azaguié	Anyama I	Anyama II
Number of species	52	44	48	46	47
Number of families	28	20	23	27	24
Number of orders	8	6	5	6	7
Abundance	6167	6104	8940	6765	7612
Hilsenhoff's Index	3,41	1,61	2,58	1,93	2,14

RESULTS

Physical and chemical variables

A summary of the environmental variables collected at the study stations is given in Table 2. The mean value of electrical conductivity was high in Layo (3037.83 \pm 2980.25 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and low in Banco (35.85 \pm 2.88 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). Dissolved oxygen was low in Banco (4.18 \pm 1.15 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and high in Anyama I (6.33 \pm 0.44 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$). The highest value of temperature (28.97 \pm 1.10 $^\circ\text{C}$) was in Azaguié while the lowest value (27.20 \pm 0.60 $^\circ\text{C}$) was recorded in Banco. The maximum transparency level (30.14 \pm 4.25 cm) was recorded in Banco while the lowest (21.65 \pm 6.84 cm) was recorded in Layo. The pH value (7.08 \pm 0.12) was maximal in Anyama I and minimal in Banco (6.75 \pm 0.19). Nitrite values varied between 0.62 \pm 0.52 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (Anyama I) and 1.26 \pm 0.84

$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (Layo). Phosphate oscillated between 1.09 \pm 0.69 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (Anyama I) and 2.47 \pm 1.44 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (Layo). Banco ammonium was significantly greater compared to other stations. Spatial variation showed significant difference ($P < 0.005$) between the stations in the different physical and chemical variables.

Taxonomic richness and abundance

A total of 79 taxa belonging to 35 families and 8 orders (Ephemeroptera, Odonata, Heteroptera, Lepidoptera, Coleoptera, Trichoptera, Megaloptera and Diptera) were obtained during the survey (Table 2). However, 72.16% of the total aquatic insect taxa richness was attributed to three taxonomic groups that included Heteroptera (21 taxa), Coleoptera (21 taxa), and Diptera (15 taxa). Chironomidae was the family who had the highest number of taxa (11 taxa). Heteroptera, with 66.45% of the total abundance, dominated quantitatively in all sampling stations. Family

Notonectidae (Heteroptera) dominated the abundance in all stations except Banco. In this station, abundance was dominated by family Chironomidae (Figure 2). The contribution of family Notonectidae to total abundance was 5292 ind. in Azaguié, 4762 ind. in Anyama II, 4135 ind. in Anyama I, 3135 ind. in Layo and 684 ind. in Banco. Consequently, the total abundance ranged from 6104 ind. in Layo to 8940 ind. in Azaguié. Table 4 summarizes variations of the number of taxa and abundance among stations.

Figure 2. Relative abundance of aquatic insect families in the different stations.

Characterization of the ponds using aquatic insects

Figure 3. Variation of Hilsenhoff's Family Biotic Index of the different study stations during Dry season (FBI 1) and Rainy season (FBI 2).

Table 4 and Figure 3 shows spatial and temporal variation of the different stations Hilsenhoff's Index during the study. The water quality is changing both spatially and temporally. Spatially, FBI values ranged from 1.61 (Layo) to 3.41 (Banco). Stations of Banco, Layo and Azaguié show little temporal variation of the Hilsenhoff's Index. The stations of Anyama I and Anyama II exhibit a higher temporal variation of FBI. In Dry season FBI values were lower in Layo and Azaguié stations. In the other hand, FBI values were lower in rainy season in Banco, Anyama I and

Anyama II stations. The water quality was excellent in the different stations. The seasonal taxonomic distribution of aquatic insects based on the Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) is presented in Figures 4 and 5. The CCA made on the abundance of aquatic insects collected relates the community structure at different stations.

Figure 4. Biplot of Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) showing distribution of different aquatic insect families in relation to the different sampling in Dry season. Abbreviation is described in Table 3.

Figure 5. Biplot of Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) showing distribution of different aquatic insect families in relation to the different sampling in Rainy season. Abbreviation is described in Table 3.

Aquatic insect in Dry season

In Dry season, the first CCA axis explained 65.83% of the observed variability in species abundance whereas the second axis captured about 16.57% of the variance for a total of 82.40%. Station of Layo where conductivity, nitrite and phosphorus were higher was characterized by a group of essential polluo-resistant taxa comprising Libellulidae, Coenagrionidae, Dytiscidae, Pyralidae, Culicidae, Curculionidae, Corixidae, Belostomatidae, Mesovelidae and Nepidae. Banco station where mud, transparency and ammonium were very important was

characterized by a group of polluo-resistant and polluo-sensitive taxa such as Hydrophilidae, Baetidae, Pleidae, Elmidae, Naucoridae, Hydropsychidae, Chrysomelidae, Tabanidae, Polycentropodidae, Polymitarciidae and Gerridae.

The station of Azaguié where water temperature, dissolved oxygen and pH were high was preferred by Notonectidae and Spercheidae. Anyama I station where the substrate is mostly composed by clay was preferred by polluo-resistant taxa namely Caenidae, Gomphidae, Veliidae and Ceratopogonidae. In the other hand, Anyama II station with any important parameter was characterized by the presence of polluo-resistant taxa composed by Gyrinidae, Chaoboridae and Chironomidae.

Aquatic insect in Rainy season

Analysis of Figure 5 resulting from the CCA based on species abundance of Rainy season explained 87.95% of the observed variability of structure which 57.16% for axis 1 and 30.79% for axis 2. In Layo station, the values of conductivity, ammonium and phosphorus were higher. This station was preferred by polluo-resistant taxa such as Dytiscidae, Elmidae, Pyralidae, Belostomatidae, Nepidae, Curculionidae, Baetidae and Naucoridae. In Banco station, the value of transparency was higher, the substrate was mostly composed by mud. In this station, polluo-resistant and polluo-sensitive taxa were collected: Veliidae, Corixidae, Chrysomelidae, Culicidae, Pleidae, Mesovelidae, Corydalidae, Hydrophilidae, Polycentropodidae, Hydroptilidae and Polymitarciidae. In Anyama I station where the substrate was essentially composed by clay some polluo-resistant and polluo-sensitive taxa were recorded: Hydropsychidae, Caenidae, Gomphidae, Leptopodidae, Ecnomidae, Gerridae, Coenagrionidae, Chironomidae and Chaoboridae. The values of nitrite, pH, temperature and dissolved oxygen were higher in Anyama II station. In this station some polluo-resistant taxa were observed. These were Gyrinidae, Ceratopogonidae, Notonectidae and Libellulidae. Azaguié station was characterized by the presence of Spercheidae.

DISCUSSION

A total of 79 taxa belonging to 35 families and 8 orders (Ephemeroptera, Odonata, Heteroptera, Lepidoptera, Coleoptera, Trichoptera, Megaloptera and Diptera) were recorded during the present study. The recorded orders are these that were generally observed in artificial and natural ponds [20-24]. The taxonomic richness of the ponds is potentially higher. Chironomidae with 11 species was the most diverse family. Recent study reported Chironomidae as the most diverse family²⁵. Order Heteroptera dominated quantitatively aquatic insect abundance. Previous study exhibit order Odonata to be the most common order quantitatively²⁰. Notonectidae was reported as numerically the most common family of in all sites except Banco where Chironomidae dominated quantitatively aquatic insect abundance. Previous study reported Belostomatidae and Chironomidae as quantitatively abundant family [25-26]. Spatially, FBI values ranged from 1.61 to 3.41. These values were comprised between 0.00 and 3.75. Ponds water quality was excellent. Seasonal variation showed that in dry season, FBI values oscillated between 1.55 (Layo) and 3.45 (Banco). In the other hand, in rainy season FBI values varied from 1.52 (Anyama I) to 3.36 (Banco). Any deterioration of water quality was mentioned. The monitoring of water quality and of freshwater biodiversity contributes to the current focus on the ecological assessment of surface water resources [27]. In fact, biological variables have many advantages over conventional physical and chemical analyses: they integrate the effects of nutrient variables (particularly phosphorus and nitrogen in this

context) over a long period of time, they are economical and they involve a relatively low sampling effort [11]. In the past, standardized biological methods of assessment exist for running waters and for lakes, but do not apply in the specific context of small standing water bodies, such as ponds [28-30]. These methods comprise the use of individual taxonomic groups as indicators - for example, diatoms, macrophytes, invertebrates (Oligochaeta and Chironomidae), and fish. Otherwise combined method indicators are chosen (e.g. biotic/diversity indices, combinations of the Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Trichoptera taxa (EPT), or fish indices) [11]. Recent biological multi-metric approaches [31] offer new monitoring possibilities because they integrate multiple dimensions of ecological systems into interpretable reference measures. This approach has been developed by Pond Conservation in Britain [32] who applied this approach to assessing the ecological quality of ponds. Previous research on small standing water bodies in Switzerland has provided a database of 94 ponds from which metrics (selected from the available literature) could be identified and tested for their potential as indicators of pond water quality [33-34]. Recent research on ponds in Switzerland has demonstrated that there is a great potential in using aquatic insect as bioindicators for the management of the water quality of ponds [11, 35-38]. From this, we can now say that aquatic insects can be used as bioindicators for the water quality of ponds as they are for running waters. It is within this framework that we used Hilsenhoff Family Biotic Index for determination of pond's water quality of these 5 fish farms.

CONCLUSION

The study of hydrobiological quality of the ponds of the different fish farms by the biological approach (Hilsenhoff Family Biotic Index) showed homogeneity of the water quality. It was excellent. Hydrobiological analyzes showed no degradation between the different stations. The seasonal variation of the water quality is not remarkable at each station.

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